

The Influence of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as Mediation Variables (Case Study PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana)

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to analyze the influence of organizational culture and work motivation on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. The independent variables in this research are organizational culture and work motivation. The dependent variable in this research is employee performance and the mediating variable in this research is job satisfaction. The data collection techniques used in this research were observation, interviews and questionnaires. The data used is primary data and secondary data, with a research sample of 32 people who are employees of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. Hypothesis testing is carried out using a variance-based Structural Equation Model (SEM) or what is called Partial Least Square (PLS). The results of the research show that organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on job satisfaction, work motivation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, organizational culture has a significant positive effect on employee performance, work motivation has a positive and not significant effect on employee performance, job satisfaction has a positive and not significant effect on performance employees, job satisfaction is not a mediation of the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance and job satisfaction is not a mediation of work motivation on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Culture, Work Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the era of industrial revolution 4.0 and free markets in all industrial fields is currently very tight so that every business actor is required to improve company performance in order to compete in a healthy manner. One sector that is experiencing rapid growth with intense competition is the banking sector, especially the growth and development of Rural Banks (BPR). Banking companies are required to be able to compete in order to maintain the survival of their companies, so as to obtain profits that can be used to pay for all types of operational costs.

Good human resources will be owned by companies that manage their resources well to produce good performance (Rivai, 2005). Good employee performance will have an impact on the company's overall performance, which can ultimately be seen from the company's achievements.

PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana is a people's credit bank located in Gianyar Regency. Established in 1993, PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana continues to develop amidst high levels of competition with commercial banks and other financial institutions. To face increasing business competition, PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana realizes that good bank performance will increase public trust

Table 1. State of Performance PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Year	Asset Growth (Rp)	Credit Distribution (Rp)	Third-party funds (Rp)
2021	103,663,330	74,312,137	89.128.331
2022	111,530,210	69,634,410	95,603,806
2023	112,345,524	57,015,873	91,562,735

Source: Financial Report PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Based on the data in Table 1.1 above, asset growth has increased in 2022 and 2023 when compared to the previous year, namely 2021. This increase shows that the company is performing better, but is not supported by the growth in credit distribution which has decreased in 2022 and 2021. 2023. Meanwhile, the amount of third party funds in 2022 increased, and again showed a decline in 2023. The decline in company performance is closely related to the achievement of employee work targets. The work targets set by the company have not been achieved optimally in the last 2 years.

Performance is the result of work achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. Employee performance is very necessary, because with this performance it will be known how far the employee's ability is to carry out the tasks assigned to him. For this reason, it is necessary to jointly determine clear and measurable criteria that can be used as a reference. This is in accordance with the explanation of goal setting theory which explains that setting goals that are challenging (difficult) and whose results can be measured will improve employee performance.

According to Subagia (2020), one of the factors that can improve employee performance is job satisfaction. Companies must realize that humans basically have various kinds of needs which are increasing over time. Companies must of course pay attention to the level of satisfaction of their employees by providing adequate welfare. Job satisfaction is closely related to employee performance (Sinambela, 2012). Employees who are satisfied with their work will certainly have loyalty to the company, they will carry out the work assigned to them with full responsibility. Job satisfaction is one of the main concerns in organizations, because employees who do not feel comfortable at work, are less appreciated, cannot develop all the potential they have, then automatically employees cannot focus and concentrate fully on their work.

Supported by research by Subagia and Safrianto (2020) which explains that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance. Employees who are satisfied with what they get from the company will provide more than what the company expects with high satisfaction and they will continue to try to improve their performance. Meanwhile, research conducted by Syardiansyah, et al (2020) found that job satisfaction did not have a significant effect on employee performance.

Apart from job satisfaction, organizational culture factors can also influence employee performance. Organizational culture is a shared perception held by members of an organization as a system of organizational values held by members of the organization, which then influences the way of working and behaving of members of the organization, so that the value system or meaning system is able to differentiate one organization from another. Robbins and Judge (2016:284) state that a strong culture will have a big influence on the behavior of its members because the high level of togetherness and intensity creates an internal climate of high behavioral control. In essence, all organizations have a culture, but not all organizational cultures are equally strong in influencing the behavior and actions of employees. The higher the level of employee acceptance of the organization's core values and the greater their commitment to these values, the stronger the organizational culture. However, a strong culture also has weaknesses, namely that a strong organizational culture tends to prevent employees from daring to try new ways, especially in dealing with rapidly changing situations. In this case it is clear that the culture embedded in the organization has a significant contribution to employee performance. When employees understand the values that exist in their organization, it will influence how they perform. Research related to the influence of organizational culture on employee performance conducted by Niam (2019) and Haan (2022) found that organizational culture had a significant effect on employee performance, while research by Girsang (2019) found that organizational culture had no effect on employee performance.

Apart from organizational culture, a factor that influences employee performance is motivation. Motivation is a desire within a person that causes the person to act. Edwin A. Locke (1968) stated that employees are more motivated by clear goals and constructive feedback and are more likely to achieve these goals if they are specific and measurable. According to Maslow (Syarmila, et al, 2022) that every person has a number of needs and at the same time determines a person's motivational structure which will drive a person's behavior in achieving their goals. People act for one reason, namely to achieve goals. So, motivation is an impulse that is governed by goals and rarely appears in a vacuum (Khairunisa, 2022). Providing motivation is very important in every company.

According to Niam (2019), this motivation is what encourages and directs the enthusiasm of an employee to always work hard and excel in completing their work in particular and ensuring the achievement of the company's mission in general. Without motivation, an employee cannot fulfill his work according to standards or exceed standards because what motivates him to work is not fulfilled. Even if an employee has high work ability but does not have the motivation to complete his duties, the final results of his work will not be satisfactory. The relationship between the influence of motivation on employee performance can be seen from

previous research. Research conducted by Antika, et al (2021), Syarmila, et al (2022), found that motivation has a significant effect on employee performance, but research conducted by Hidayat (2021), found that motivation has no effect on employee performance.

Related to the phenomenon that exists at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana and the results of previous research show that employee performance is determined by job satisfaction, motivation and organizational culture. However, previous research is inconsistent so it is necessary to re-examine the influence of organizational culture and work motivation on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable at PT BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Goal Setting Theory

Goal setting theory developed by Locke (1968) has begun to attract interest in various organizational problems and issues. According to goal setting theory, individuals have several goals, choose goals, and they are motivated to achieve the goals. This theory assumes that the main factor influencing the choices individuals make is the goals they have. Goal setting theory has shown a significant influence in the formulation of goals. Specificity and difficulty are attributes of goal setting. Generally, the more difficult and specific the goals set, the higher the level of achievement that will result (Locke & Lathan., 2020).

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory

According to Maslow ((Pranata, 2014), the level of work motivation varies between individuals and within an individual at different times. Perhaps it can be said that the most famous work motivation theory is the hierarchy of needs expressed by Abraham Maslow. There are five the most important needs to the least crucial:

- 1) Basic physiological needs, namely basic daily human needs for eating, drinking, clothing, shelter and other physical needs.
- 2) The need to feel safe is the need for protection from bodily injury, threats, a sense of security at work and other needs.
- 3) Social Needs, namely to belong, be recognized, love, integrate and be accepted in the social work group.
- 4) The need for self-esteem is an employee's need for recognition, status, honor and appreciation.
- 5) Actualization needs are human needs to demonstrate the abilities and potential that exist within themselves in working to achieve maximum work results.

Employee performance

According to Rivai & Basri (2005: 15-16), performance is the willingness of a person or group of people to carry out an activity and perfect it in accordance with their responsibilities with the expected results. According to Luthans (Paparang, 2021:119), performance is the quantity or quality of something produced or a service provided by someone doing the work. Performance is the result or overall level of success of a person during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as standards of work results, targets or goals or criteria that have been determined in advance and have been mutually agreed upon. According to Bernardin and Russell (Wiguna, 2022) there are six indicators of employee performance, namely: work quality, work quantity, timeliness, supervision requirements, interpersonal impact, and cost effectiveness.

Job Satisfaction

Courtney & Younkyoung (Abuhashes et al, 2019:3), job satisfaction is an individual's subjective perspective and the way he feels about his work and the work of his organization. In addition, job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional state that results from achieving work values. The indicators that determine job satisfaction according to Robbins (Prasetyo, 2019) are work that is mentally challenging, supportive working conditions, appropriate salary or wages, suitability of personality to the job, supportive colleagues.

Organizational Culture

In Zaky (2021), Schein states that organizational culture is a set of values, norms, beliefs and behaviors shared by members of an organization, which form expected patterns of behavior and help direct individual actions in the organization. According to Mangkunegara (Syardiansah, 2020), the definition of organizational culture is a set of assumptions or system of beliefs, values and norms developed within an organization which serve as behavioral guidelines for its members to overcome problems of external adaptation and internal integration. Indicators of organizational culture according to Robbins (2005:485) are: innovation and taking risk, attention to detail, results orientation, individual orientation, team orientation.

Work Motivation

According to Kanfer (Syarmila, 2022), in general work motivation can be interpreted as a psychological process that directs all a person's energy, thoughts and feelings in determining their attitudes or actions both in relation to other people and towards their work. Work motivation is an effort that can generate behavior, direct it, and maintain or maintain behavior that is appropriate to the work environment (Khairunisa, et al, 2022). Work motivation is the willingness to make high efforts to achieve company goals, which is conditioned by the ability to meet certain individual needs in accordance with work results (Robins and Judge, 2013). The work motivation factors according to Herzberg in Heriyanto and Hidayati (2016) are: the work itself, achievements achieved, opportunities for advancement, recognition from others, responsibility.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.
- H2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
- H3: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- H4: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- H5: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- H6: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance.
- H7: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between work motivation and employee performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research used in this research is a quantitative approach, the research variables in this research are exogenous variables and endogenous variables. The dependent variable in this research is employee performance and the mediating variable in this research is job satisfaction. The data collection techniques used in this research were observation, interviews and questionnaires. The data used is primary data and secondary data, with a research sample of 32 people who are employees of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana.

The data analysis technique used is SEM- Partial Least Square analysis. In analyzing the influence between exogenous and endogenous variables in this research, Partial Least Square (PLS) is used because this method does not require many assumptions, including the assumption of normality, and is popularly used in complex studies that are not supported by adequate theory.

In testing the research instrument, IBM-SPSS software was used to test the validity and reliability of the results of distributing the questionnaire. Next, the data is processed using the SmartPLS application to determine the influence between the relationships between each variable.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

Structural Model Evaluation

The results of this research obtained an outer loading value above 0.60 after reconstructing the model by removing indicators that had factor loading values below 0.60. This means that indicators that have a value above 0.70 can measure the latent variable well.

The composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values for each construct are greater than 0.70. The employee performance construct has composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values of 0.892 and 0.846. The job satisfaction construct has composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values of 0.888 and 0.851. The work motivation construct has composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values of 0.869 and 0.815. The organizational culture construct has composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values of 0.891 and 0.848. The calculation recapitulation results can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Structural Model Evaluation Test Results

Construct	Outer Loading	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Y 2.1 <- Employee Performance	0.810		
Y 2.2 <- Employee Performance	0.777		

Y 2.3 <- Employee Performance	0.640	0.892	0.846
Y 2.4 <- Employee Performance	0.864		
Y 2.5 <- Employee Performance	0.844		
Y 1.1 <- Job Satisfaction	0.830	0.888	0.851
Y 1.2 <- Job Satisfaction	0.620		
Y 1.3 <- Job Satisfaction	0.763		
Y 1.4 <- Job Satisfaction	0.796		
Y 1.5 <- Job Satisfaction	0.751		
Y 1.6 <- Job Satisfaction	0.762		
X 1.1 <- Organizational Culture	0.774	0.891	0.848
X 1.2 <- Organizational Culture	0.851		
X 1.3<- Organizational Culture	0.750		
X 1.4<- Organizational Culture	0.790		
X 1.5<- Organizational Culture	0.774		
X 2.1 <- Work Motivation	0.845	0.869	0.815
X 2.2 <- Work Motivation	0.803		
X 2.3 <- Work Motivation	0.628		
X 2.4 <- Work Motivation	0.652		
X 2.5 <- Work Motivation	0.831		

Source: Calculation Results with the PLS Program

R-Square & Q-Square

R-Square Job satisfaction of 0.46 is included in the criteria for a model that is close to strong, meaning that the constructs of organizational culture and motivation can explain variations in job satisfaction of 46 percent, while the remaining 54 percent is explained by variations in other variables outside the research model. Meanwhile, employee performance has an R-Square index value of 0.81, including a strong model, meaning that organizational culture, motivation and job satisfaction can explain 81 percent of performance variations, while the remaining 19 percent is influenced by other constructs that are not analyzed in the estimation model.

Q2 employee performance = 0.42. Based on Lathan and Ghozali's criteria, it is included in the strong model criteria. The Q2 value for job satisfaction of 0.21 is also included in the moderate to strong model. This means that the mathematical model built in this research has a high level of predictive accuracy. The calculation recapitulation results can be seen in table 3 and table 4.

Table 3. R-Square Results

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Job satisfaction	0.462	0.425
Employee performance	0.809	0.778

Source: PLS calculation results

Table 4 Q-Square Results

Total	Case1	Case2	Case3	Case4	Case5
	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)		
BUDAYA ORGANISASI	160.000	160.000			
KEPUASAN KERJA	192.000	151.354			0.212
KINERJA KARYAWAN	160.000	92.107			0.424
MOTIVASI	160.000	160.000			

Evaluation of Structural Models via Goodness of Fit (GoF)

Goodness of Fit (GoF) is a measurement of the accuracy of the model as a whole, because it is considered to be a single measurement of outermodel measurements and inner model measurements. The criteria for whether a model is strong or weak based on GoF measurements according to Wetzels et al (Yamin, 2022), are as **Path Hypothesis Analysis and Testing** follows: 0.36 (GoF large)/model with high suitability, 0.25 (medium GoF), and 0.10 (GoF small). Akter et al (2011) suggest a cut off value of 0.36. The GoF formula is $= \sqrt{A.R^2 * A.AVE}$
 $= \sqrt{0.63 * 0.59} = 0.61$ (R2 is taken from Table 5.8 and the AVE value is from Table 5.7). These results indicate that the model built is a large model, meaning that the model meets the requirements as a fit model.

Table 5. Direct Effects

Variable	Original Sample	T statistics	P values	Information
Organizational Culture -> Job Satisfaction	0.248	0.971	0.332	Not significant
Organizational Culture > Employee Performance	0.664	0.5267	0,000	Significant
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.282	1,637	0.102	Not significant
Motivation > Job Satisfaction	0.491	2,123	0.034	Significant
Motivation -> Performance	0.059	0.403	0.687	Not significant

Source: PLS Calculation Results

Table 6. Indirect Effects

Path Coefficients	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Organizational Culture -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.070	0.871	0.384	Not significant
Work Motivation -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.138	1,038	0.300	Not significant

Source: PLS Calculation Results

1. Organizational culture has a positive effect of 0.248 but is not significant on employee job satisfaction. This means that a better organizational culture does not necessarily increase employee job satisfaction.
2. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect of 0.664 on performance, meaning that the better the organizational culture, the more significantly performance will increase.
3. Job satisfaction has a positive effect of 0.282 but is not significant on employee performance. This means that higher job satisfaction will not necessarily improve employee performance.
4. Work motivation has a positive effect of 0.491 and is significant on job satisfaction. This means that the higher the work motivation, the more job satisfaction will increase significantly.
5. Work motivation has a positive effect of 0.059 but is not significant on employee performance. This means that increasing work motivation is not necessarily able to improve employee performance.
6. Job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance. This can be seen from the direct relationship between organizational culture and performance which is significant, but the indirect relationship between organizational culture and performance through job satisfaction is not significant. This means that apart from job satisfaction there are other constructs that mediate organizational culture in improving performance, such as discipline, regulations and compensation.
7. Job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between work motivation and employee performance. This can be seen from the direct relationship between work motivation and employee performance which is not significant, but the indirect relationship

between motivation and performance through job satisfaction is also not significant. This means that apart from job satisfaction there are other constructs that mediate work motivation in improving performance, such as discipline and compensation.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction at PT BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction, a significance level of $0.332 > 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was accepted and H_1 was rejected, which means that organizational culture has a positive and insignificant effect on the job satisfaction of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees. This shows that a better organizational culture does not necessarily result in higher job satisfaction for employees of PT BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. A significance level above 0.05 means that organizational culture is able to increase job satisfaction but is not significant or not optimal.

This research found that organizational culture is not a factor that influences employee job satisfaction. The results of this research are in accordance with those conducted by Junaidi (2022) who explained that organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This gives the result that work culture is unable to encourage how employee behavior is seen as something that has an important role in achieving the ultimate goals of an institution. The existence of other factors besides organizational culture can influence employee satisfaction, such as leadership style and compensation. Lack of values in organizational culture at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana regarding work discipline and its application in employee work behavior is one of the factors that makes employees unable to complete their work well. This has an impact on work results that are not optimal and do not match the company's targets. This situation means that the compensation received by employees is not optimal, resulting in dissatisfaction.

The Influence of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana Employees

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of work motivation on job satisfaction, a significance level of $0.034 < 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was rejected and H_2 was accepted, which means that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees. This shows that the higher the employee's work motivation, the higher the job satisfaction of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees. A significance level below 0.05 means that work motivation significantly influences the level of employee job satisfaction.

Workers who have strong motivation will generally behave positively. This positive behavior will influence the work environment. However, on the other hand, if the work attitude is bad, it will have an impact on the poor work environment so that it will also have an impact on job satisfaction in general (Niam, 2019).

Work motivation is an important factor in influencing job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is job satisfaction enjoyed at work by receiving praise for work results, placement, equipment and a good work environment. Motivated employees will feel satisfaction at work so they can improve their performance. These results are in accordance with research by Niam, et al (2019), Irwan, et al (2020), Parma (2020), Yuliantika (2020), Sembiring, et al (2021), Rachmaniah (2022), and Putri (2023) who found work motivation significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on PT Employee Performance. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of organizational culture on employee performance, a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was rejected and H_3 was accepted, which means that organizational culture has a significant positive effect on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This shows that the better the organizational culture, the more the performance of PT employees will improve. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. A significance level below 0.05 means that there is a significant influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

Organizational culture is the values that guide human resources in dealing with external problems and efforts to adjust integration into the company so that each member of the organization must understand the existing values and how they should act or behave. Factors such as values, norms, beliefs, behavior, human resource management practices, leadership, and cultural adaptation all contribute to creating a work environment that is conducive for employees to achieve higher performance. The same results can be found in the results of research conducted by Niam and Syah (2019), Panggabean MS, et al (2020), Syardiansah, et al (2020), Haan, et al (2022), and Sudaryono (2023) which reveal that there is an influence positive and significant organizational culture on employee performance.

The Influence of Work Motivation on PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana Employee Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of work motivation on employee performance, a significance level of $0.687 > 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was accepted and H_4 was rejected, which means that work motivation had a positive but not significant effect on the performance of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees. This shows that high work motivation has a slow or non-optimal effect on the performance of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees.

This research found that employee performance was not significantly influenced by work motivation. The existence of other factors also has an influence on increasing employee performance at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana such as capability factors relating to employee potential and education level. Apart from that, the lack of appreciation from superiors makes employees demotivated to complete their work. So employees are unable to complete their work well.

The same results were also found in research by Yuliantika (2020), Khairunisa and Gulo (2022), Wijaya (2023) which revealed that work motivation was positively but not significantly influenced by employee performance.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana Employee Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of job satisfaction on employee performance, a significance level of $0.102 > 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was accepted and H_5 was rejected, which means that job satisfaction has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This shows that high job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on the performance of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana employees.

Improving employee performance is strongly supported by job satisfaction. However, this was not found in research at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. That employee performance is not maximally influenced by job satisfaction. This shows that there are factors other than job satisfaction that influence employee performance, such as the level of work discipline or good supervision from superiors. The results of this research support the results of research conducted by Syardiansah, et al (2020), Sembiring, et al (2021), and Lestari, et al (2022) which stated that job satisfaction does not have a significant effect on employee performance.

The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Relationship between Organizational Culture and PT Employee Performance. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Based on the results of the analysis of the mediating influence of organizational culture on employee performance through job satisfaction, a significance level of $0.384 > 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was accepted and H_6 was rejected, which means that job satisfaction was unable to mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This shows that there are things other than job satisfaction that mediate organizational culture in improving performance. The results of this research are the same as research conducted by Niam and Syah (2019) which states that job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance.

The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating the Relationship between Work Motivation and Employee Performance of PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of motivation on performance through job satisfaction, a significance level of $0.300 > 0.05$ was obtained, so that H_0 was accepted and H_7 was rejected, which means that job satisfaction was unable to mediate the influence of work motivation on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This shows that work motivation does not significantly influence employee performance through job satisfaction.

The amount of work motivation given to employees cannot improve employee performance through job satisfaction at PT. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that apart from job satisfaction there are other things that mediate work motivation in improving employee performance.

The results of this research support research conducted by Darmawan and Tanuwijaya (2023) which revealed that work motivation has no effect on employee performance through job satisfaction. So job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between work motivation and employee performance.

THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This research has investigated the relationship between direct and indirect influence between organizational culture and work motivation on job satisfaction and its impact on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This research was conducted to overcome the gap between research paradigms, and seeks to determine the mediation of job satisfaction on the

relationship between organizational culture and work motivation and employee performance. Some of the contributions of this research are in accordance with existing theories, but some are contradictory. Namely that the relationship between organizational culture and work motivation on job satisfaction has an insignificant impact on employee performance.

Future research should develop this research regarding factors other than organizational culture and work motivation that can influence employee performance by using an integrative framework or other variables as mediating variables besides job satisfaction.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

High performance is something that an organization, both profit-oriented and non-profit organizations, wants to achieve. The results of this research show that organizational culture is a factor that influences job satisfaction directly but is not significant and does not have an impact on increasing employee performance. So it is necessary to implement organizational values that can further increase employee job satisfaction, so that they can have a direct and optimal impact on employee performance. Meanwhile, work motivation shows a significant influence on job satisfaction but does not have a direct impact on employee performance. Apart from that, it is also necessary to further improve the provision of work motivation both externally and internally, such as conducting employee training, so that there is an increase in work motivation which will have an impact on job satisfaction as well as increasing employee performance.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

Only examining the relationship between organizational culture variables, work motivation, job satisfaction and employee performance. The results of this research cannot be generalized to other organizations, meaning that this research is only able to explain the situation among PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana, with its unique organizational characteristics and other factors within the organization.

The data used refers to data collected by observing individuals and companies at the same point in time or without paying attention to time differences, that is, comparing differences between subjects so that they are only temporary and research needs to be carried out periodically and continuously so that they can be used as material for long-term policy considerations.

The answers given by respondents to the items in the questionnaire will of course be greatly influenced by the character, condition and understanding of each respondent when answering. There is a possibility that respondents' answers do not match the actual facts.

CONCLUSION

1. Organizational culture has a positive and insignificant effect on job satisfaction of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that the better the organizational culture does not have an optimal impact on employee job satisfaction.
2. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that the higher work motivation will increase job satisfaction.
3. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that the better the organizational culture will improve employee performance.
4. Work motivation has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that the higher work motivation does not lead to increased employee performance.
5. Job satisfaction has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of PT employees. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana. This means that the higher the level of job satisfaction will not have an impact on increasing employee performance.
6. Job satisfaction is unable to mediate the relationship between organizational culture and PT employee performance. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana
7. Job satisfaction is unable to mediate the relationship between work motivation and PT employee performance. BPR Eka Ayu Artha Bhuwana.

SUGGESTION

1. For companies, to be able to improve employee performance, they need to do things such as:
 - a. Provide more encouragement for employees to innovate and dare to take risks, in order to create a better organizational culture.

- b. Provide praise and appreciation when employees show good performance, so that employees feel appreciated and motivated to further improve their performance. Apart from that, it is necessary to hold more frequent trainings that can increase employees' internal motivation for their respective jobs.
 - c. Implementing a salary system that is more appropriate for improving employee welfare, as well as a policy of providing promotions on the basis of better work performance.
 - d. Implement better work targets and time limits for achieving work targets and impose certain consequences if they are not achieved, such as cutting bonuses.
2. Employees should apply more of the values that constitute the company's organizational culture. Apart from that, you should always actively participate in training organized by the company for the sake of personal progress which will have an impact on performance. It is also necessary to increase discipline and accuracy in completing work according to the target and time that has been set.
3. For further research, it is hoped that this research can be developed using factors other than organizational culture and work motivation to analyze variables that can influence employee performance, such as leadership, work quality, work ability, initiative, reliability, work quantity and work discipline. Apart from that, you can use mediating variables other than job satisfaction, such as compensation or discipline, to determine the indirect relationship to employee performance

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